

ROLE OF WOMEN AND GENDER EQUALITY IN RENEWING UZBEKISTAN

Nurmukhamidova M.Kh.

Senior teacher, Gulistan State University

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Abstract. *The article describes the effective use of entrepreneurial potential in ensuring women's employment and its important directions. Issues of ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of women were considered.*

Keywords: *gender equality, employment, entrepreneurship, sustainable development, labor contract, human capital, "Women's notebook", preferential loan.*

Our nation has paid special attention to women since time immemorial. First of all, our women are valued and respected as mothers. The reason is that both our current prosperous life and our bright future directly depend on them.

Today, our women are self-sacrificing in raising children, in various fields, in their neighborhoods. In recent years, a number of laws, decrees and decisions have been adopted in order to ease their burden and ensure their rights and interests.

Women make up more than 17 million of the population of Uzbekistan, and the share of women in entrepreneurship is 25% of the total number of small business representatives. One of the priority tasks facing this direction is to increase the share of women among business entities to 40 percent. Favorable conditions are being created for this, a lot of work has been done in this regard.

Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women was defined as one of the main goals and objectives of Uzbekistan in the field of sustainable development until 2030. Laws "On protection of women and girls from harassment and violence" and "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women, girls and men" were adopted. With this, the conditions for further increasing the social activity of women, eliminating all forms of discrimination against them, ensuring gender equality, and preventing various oppression and violence against women were further strengthened. In order to implement the gender policy in the civil service, the law temporarily introduces a quota body for employees of the same sex. That is, temporary gender quotas are set until the proportional representation of women and men is ensured in each state enterprise and organization. Once balance is reached, quotas can be waived. In particular, the Law on "Gender Equality" creates the ground for increasing the role of women in the social and political spheres of public administration.

It should be noted that the 5th goal of "Uzbekistan's national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030" adopted on the basis of the UN Sustainable Development Goals is to ensure gender equality and the rights and opportunities of all women. aimed at expanding". This document created more opportunities for ensuring gender equality in our society. On March 7, 2019, the decision PQ-4235 "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship" hindered the social and political activity of women. Some factors have been put an end to. In particular, even when women reach the retirement age (55 years old), it is forbidden to cancel the employment contract concluded with them at the initiative of the employer until they reach the age of 60; it was determined that if the

services of lawyers are needed in cases related to the violation of gender equality, these services will be covered by the state; bans on the use of women's labor in certain fields or professions were abolished; preferential loans were allocated for women engaged in business activities, as a result of which the number of women entrepreneurs has exceeded 14,000.

A wide path has been opened for women to directly participate in the implementation of decisions affecting the fate of the state and society, in particular, in the processes of developing, adopting and implementing laws.

Because at the same time, in the project of the State program on the implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy in the "Year of supporting youth and business", which is currently under public discussion, there are a number of tasks to raise the work in this direction to a new level. reflected.

In particular, support for women's employment, development of entrepreneurship among them, vocational training and self-employment are given priority. means that he will have a job and a source of income.

The question of helping to ensure the employment of women and girls by training them in competitive professions in the labor market and the wide development of entrepreneurship among them is also being determined. These tasks are in harmony with the goals and ideas of our party, and it is important that they provide the employment of women and create a basis for directing them to a certain profession.

To train young women in modern professions such as entrepreneurship, marketing, graphic design, launching the platform "Girls' Academy" and organizing various contests, projects, training camps, and internships for young women is the main criterion. These good deeds will be another important step in strengthening the social protection of the population and ensuring human rights.

Today, our women, who are the angels of grace in every household, who make a worthy contribution to raising children as well-rounded people, actively participate in all our reforms. Providing constant attention and care to women is an integral part of the state policy in Uzbekistan.

Therefore, the work of ensuring women's employment, further increasing their role and influence in state and community management, expanding the conditions for them to show their potential, protecting gender equality, family, motherhood and childhood has reached a new level.

The adoption of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 was literally a historical event. This historical programming document, which is a logical continuation of the action strategy, clearly defines the development trends of Uzbekistan in the near and medium term, as well as directions for comprehensive development of all aspects of state and community life.

In the development strategy, prospects for the development of Uzbekistan in the next 5 years are determined. In this regard, it is planned to implement 100 goals "For human dignity" in the following seven priority areas:

- establishment of a people-friendly state by increasing human dignity and further development of a free civil society;
 - making the principles of justice and the rule of law the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country;
 - rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates;
 - conducting a fair social policy, developing human capital;
 - ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level;

— to approach universal problems based on national interests;
- strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy.

The 69th goal of the development strategy is called "Supporting women and girls, ensuring their active participation in the life of society." It includes:

- Increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life in 2022-2026;
- creating additional conditions for women's education, further increasing the position of women in the field of science;
- organization of free educational practical courses for the formation of business skills among women, allocation of preferential loans and leases, establishment of cooperative entrepreneurship by involving women in work;
- Reimbursement of medical treatment expenses of women who are included in the "Women's register" and need to undergo surgery;
- To study and analyze the practice of solving women's problems through the "Ayollar daftari" and, based on the experience gained, systematically solve women's problems and provide them with social support by maintaining the "Ayollar daftari". tasks such as the development of drafts of model regulations on the women's support fund included in the "Ayollar daftari".

In addition, the 60th goal of the Development Strategy is to provide high-tech medical care for reproductive age and pregnant women and children, and the 85th goal is to reduce the unemployment rate among women by 2 times, to employ more than 80,000 unemployed women at the expense of the state. - implementation of comprehensive measures for vocational training, entrepreneurship and self-employment of women, development of a program for the development of women's entrepreneurship in regions, organization of "Women's handicraft centers" and clusters in each region issues are covered.

At the same time, urgent tasks such as improving the activities of women's entrepreneurship centers, taking steps to open regional centers, assisting in the sale of products produced by women entrepreneurs, training women in entrepreneurship and attracting them to business have been defined.

Just one example: loans of up to 33 million soums at an annual rate of 14 percent with a grace period of up to 3 years and up to 6 months are allocated from the Women's Support State Target Fund to start a business. Credits to the following programs:

- Training courses based on programs approved by the Agency for Entrepreneurship Development and the Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship;
- Successfully completed the special training programs of "Ishga Marhamat" monocenters, vocational training centers, neighborhood vocational training centers and Women's Entrepreneurship Centers or non-state educational institutions. given to women.

In conclusion, from the Development Strategy and the State Program for the current year, comprehensive support for our women, strengthening the health of mothers and children, providing them with free medicines and vitamins, developing physical education, education of young girls. There are many issues such as employment, all of which are an example of the real care shown by the state and society for the women of our country.

Therefore, the implementation of measures aimed at encouraging active, entrepreneurial women and farmers, who make a significant contribution to the development of the country, the

welfare of the people and the implementation of innovative projects, popularizing their activities and advanced work experience cannot be delayed.

Therefore, it is necessary to further increase the influence of women in our social and political life, who have an incomparable role in strengthening the atmosphere of peace and kindness in our society, bringing the young generation to adulthood in a healthy and mature manner. Decent conditions for them, creation of new jobs, alleviating the burden of our sisters, and the consistent reforms that are being implemented to ensure their gender equality, expanding the efforts of women in this regard, and the implementation of our society serves as an important factor in deepening democratic reforms and improving the development of our country.

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